

Implementation of Universal Basic Education Programme in Lagos State Schools: Counsellors' and Teachers' Perceptions

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Abstract

Nigeria having realized the effectiveness of education as a powerful instrument for national development inaugurated Universal Basic Education (UBE) in with some specific goals and objectives which require all stakeholders including counsellors to play their parts in its implementation. This study was therefore a 3x2 factorial survey design to appraise perceptions of counsellors and teachers on the quality implementation of Universal Basic Education programme in Lagos State schools. Two hundred (200) counsellors and teachers were randomly selected for this study in Lagos Primary and Junior Secondary Schools. The research instrument for data collection was a self-developed questionnaire titled "Counsellors and Teachers Perception of Universal Basic Education Scale" (COTPUBES). The instrument was validated in terms of its content and construct while its reliability was established after analysis at 0.74 level of correlation coefficient using Cronbach's alpha method through the single method of administration. Three hypotheses were postulated to guide the study. The data collected were analysed using mean(x), Standard Deviation (SD), ANOVA, Chi-square and t-test. Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that counsellors are the backbone of any educational programme. Therefore, the usage of their skills through guidance services at all levels to enhance quality of education cannot be over emphasized. It was also suggested among other things that encouraging professional development, in-service-training, motivation and mentoring counsellors will make counsellors to perform more in providing support services for UBE to be more effective.

Keywords: Counsellors, Implementation, Perceptions, Teachers, Universal Basic Education

Introduction

Education is the process of facilitating learning, or the acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, beliefs, and habits. It is one of the vital instruments in development 'per excellence' for effective national development. It has been empirically proved and universally acknowledged that unless the citizens of a nation are well educated and appropriately trained, the achievements of rapid economic and social development of such a nation cannot be guaranteed (Olukolade & Okuwa, 2012). Therefore, education has become one of the most powerful weapons known for reducing poverty and inequality in modern societies. It is also used for laying the foundation for

sustainable growth and development of any nation. Education plays a critical role in the development of a nation. It equips citizens with requisite knowledge, skills and competencies. What students require to be productive and to succeed in the global economy are knowledge, skills, values and habits they need to thrive in a future driven by globalization and technological advancements with a blend of academic works and skills such as critical thinking, problem solving and creativity; as well as literacies that can be applied in another critical situation. Thus, educational institutions are challenged to review regularly their programmes, curricular, teaching methods and learning environments to adapt to these new demands. Education sector must transform itself to improve its capacity to play this significant role throughout the students' learning journey, beginning with sound early childhood education through universal basic education to senior secondary and higher education (Okpala, 2014).

Primary education is the foundation for development and progress in modern societies. It is the level of education that develops in the individual the capacity to read, write and calculate. In other words, it helps to eradicate illiteracy, which is one of the strongest predictors of poverty (Bruns, Mingart & Rakotomalal, 2003). Thus, primary education is the only level of education that is available everywhere in both the developed and the developing countries as well as in urban and rural areas (Akinbote, 2001). This explains why primary education is the largest sub-sector of any education system and offers the unique opportunity to contribute to the transformation of societies through the education of young ones (UNESCO, 2001).

Primary education is seen as the first in laying the foundation for future opportunities and lifelong skills. Through the skills and knowledge imbibed, individuals are enabled to participate in the social, economic and political activities of their communities to their maximum potentials. Primary education is also seen as a basic human right that frees human beings from a state of ignorance and helps to reduce the negative effects of poverty, relating in particular to health and nutrition (Umo, 2015). Nigeria having realized the effectiveness of education as a powerful instrument to national progress and development adjusted her educational philosophy and methodology to match the ideals and challenging economic and social structure of modern society.

The introduction of Universal Basic Education (UBE) in Nigeria emanated from the World Conference of Education for All (EFA) held in Jomitten, Thailand in 1990. It was also a response to international recognition of children education as stipulated by the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) item two which proposed that by 2015, children of school age should have free, affordable and accessible education and adopted by world nations in 2000. The Universal Basic Education (UBE) Programme is a nine (9) year basic educational programme (first nine years of schooling) which was launched and executed by the government and people of the Federal Republic of Nigeria to eradicate illiteracy, ignorance and poverty as well as stimulate and accelerate national development, political consciousness and national integration. Former President Olusegun Obasanjo flagged off UBE on 30th September 1999 in Sokoto, Sokoto State.

UBE is being implemented in Nigeria as a lasting legacy for the eradication of illiteracy because as a country, we need a universal basic education programme that will ensure that every Nigerian children is literate, and our youth on graduation are sufficiently equipped with

knowledge, skills, and experiences required of them as individuals to contribute their quota to the development of the country (Lucas, Alaka & Odozi, 2014). The basic features of the UBE programme include: free formal basic education, compulsory uninterrupted nine years of Primary and Junior Secondary School Education, emphasis on curriculum diversification and relevance to effectively and adequately cover individual and community needs and aspirations, disarticulation of Junior Secondary Schools from Senior Secondary Schools, introduction of rudiments of computer literacy, appropriate continuous teacher professional development, community ownership of schools including participation in decision-making process in schools (Domike & Odey, 2014).

The Federal Government intervention is quarterly (4 times in a year), and a counterpart fund of equal amount is expected from the states and is expended as follows: Nursery (5%), Primary (60%) and Junior Secondary School (35%), while it is disbursed at each level of education as follows: infrastructure (70%), manpower development (15%), and instructional material (15%) (Ekpunobi, 2006). A 9-year continuous free and compulsory education was proposed for immediate implementation to realize this laudable goal. The government is expected to provide classrooms, construct new buildings, and provide books and writing materials as well as all other things needed for teaching and learning in the primary schools. The government is also required, under the principles of the UBE programme, to provide textbooks, pencils, diaries, desks, chairs, board, as well as visual and audio-visual aids through the State Universal Basic Education Board (SUBEB) for onward distribution to the various schools and learning centres. Government is also expected to provide support to the physically challenged through the provision of the special learning requirements which they need (Onwubiko, 2012).

The Universal Basic Education, UBE, came as a replacement of the Universal Primary Education and an innovation to enhance the success of the first nine years of schooling. The universal aspect of UBE implies that all persons regardless of their physical and psychological conditions will benefit from the programme. Encouragement and necessary support have to be given to cater for the special needs of targeted population (Conchi-Miriam, 2012). The UBE involves 6 years of Primary School Education and 3 years of Junior Secondary School, culminating in 9 years of uninterrupted schooling, and transition from one class to another is automatic but determined through continuous assessment. Free and compulsory education was proposed for immediate implementation. Application of universal basic education is gradually becoming their responsibility not only of the government but that of the entire stakeholders.

The overall objectives of the UBE programme as contained in the Universal Basic Education Annual Report of 2001 are as follows:

- i. Developing in the entire citizenry a strong consciousness for education and a strong commitment to its vigorous promotion;
- ii. The provision of free, universal basic education for every Nigerian child of school age;
- iii. Drastically reducing the incidence of drop-out from formal school system;
- iv. Catering for the learning needs of young persons who for one reason or another, have led to the interruption of their schooling through appropriate forms of complementary approaches to the provision and promotion of basic education; and,

- v. Ensuring the acquisition of appropriate levels of literacy, numeracy, communicative and life skills as well as the ethical, moral and civic values needed for laying a solid foundation for lifelong learning.

However, Guidance and Counselling is an integral aspect of guidance services which relates to problems associated with learning, teaching and education generally. It is the assistance given to students and management with appropriate techniques to help them function more effectively. Counselling as a profession helps an individual to realize one's potentials, capabilities, interests, abilities, needs and aspirations in order to formulate one's own goals and make adequate plans for realizing the goals. Counselling draws upon the past of an individual and bring it to bear on the present of the same individual in order to fashion a future that ensures self- realization and self-actualization of such individual (Oko, 2010). Counselling is a unique profession due to its importance in the scheme of things. Counsellors must ensure that their guidance services are rendered in schools to help in facilitating efforts at giving quality education to all Nigerians (Esere, Omotosho & Eweniyi, 2010).

Guidance services are professional aids given by counsellors in schools to enhance individual growth and development, and to improve student's performance. This will help students make maximum progress and success in school subjects, have some personal meaning to his/her behaviour, and to develop realistic goals, plans, and values for further behaviours. Guidance services are needed by school children to resolve academic, vocational, social, and personal problems. The school counsellors have lots of roles to play towards the successful implementation of UBE as professionals and stakeholders through guidance services such as educating the parents of their responsibilities towards their children at school, orientation service for the new intakes, information service, appraisal service, placement service, referral service, counselling service, evaluation service, follow up services and so on laying a solid foundation for life-long learning.

Education entails more than acquisition of knowledge, it is the aggregate of one's ability, skills, attitudes, values, perception and acceptable pattern of behaviour by the society which can only be imparted by teachers. Teachers are trained and skilled professionals who are to impart the knowledge they possess to the student for betterment of the society. Teachers constitute very important component in any educational programme, they are as important as the students. The National Policy on Education (2013) has emphasised the importance of teachers in any educational system when it unequivocally stated that "no educational system can rise above the level of its teachers". The influence of teachers in an educational scheme cannot be over emphasised, as they are responsible for the overall development of the learning scheme. No matter the extent of availability of physical and material resources, if teachers are not available, they remain unproductive until they are utilised by teachers. Also, no matter how promising the curriculum is, the ideas therein can only be brought to lime light through teachers, we can therefore conclude that school cannot exist without a teacher. For the successful implementation of the UBE programme, teachers are to teach conscientiously in the classroom, they should always endeavour to improvise for teaching aids and instructional materials.

Nigerian government has good intention to fulfil Universal Basic Education purpose as stated in the National Policy on Education, but the goals of UBE remain beyond the reach of many Nigerians despite all the inherent goodness that it offers and the zeal with which it has been pursued by all stakeholders. Granted that the UBE scheme is free and compulsory, it carries with it some inevitable obligations, problems and issues that cannot be overlooked. The common concern of many people in educational circles in Nigeria today is about “falling standards” and increase in number of school age children who are drop out of school for many socio-cultural and economic reasons. The dissatisfaction with school curricula is freely expressed in the press and other public platforms by parents and general public as well. That is why it behoves counsellors, teachers and psychologists to do what is necessary to keep the standard of education from falling further. They must work hard to universalize access to UBE, engender conducive learning environment and quality that is sufficiently high enough to compete with the quality found in other parts of the world now that the programme has been extended to junior secondary schools. The need for Nigerian primary and junior secondary schools to fulfil the central purpose of primary education and provide basic skills needed to acquire permanent literacy in Nigeria necessitates the need for this study. Against this back drop, the study seeks to investigate counsellors’ and teachers’ perceptions on the implementation of Universal Basic Education in Lagos State schools.

Purpose of the Study

- i. To determine the perception of counsellors and teachers on the extent to which UBE has reduced illiteracy in Lagos State schools.
- ii. To establish the perception of counsellors on the quality of UBE implementation.
- iii. To investigate the extent of involvement of counsellors in the implementation of UBE programme.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested in this study.

HO₁ There will be no significant difference in the mean rating of counsellors and teachers about their roles in enhancing quality in the UBE programme implementation.

HO₂ There will be no significant difference in the perception of counsellors and teachers about the quality of UBE programme implementation.

HO₃ There will be no significant difference in the opinion of counsellors and teachers about the extent to which UBE programme has reduced illiteracy through the provision of quality basic education.

Method

The study was a 3x2 factorial design survey research design method. This design sought to collect information without manipulation of any variable from the respondent. This study was carried out in Lagos metropolis. Ten selected schools that included five primary and five junior secondary schools were used for the study. The target population for this study comprised all counsellors and all teachers in primary and junior secondary schools in Lagos metropolis. A

sample of two hundred counsellors and teachers were selected from ten schools in Lagos metropolis using multistage sampling techniques. The sample also comprised 80 (40%) male and 120(60%) female counsellors and teachers respectively.

The instrument used for the study was a self-designed structured questionnaire titled “Counsellors and Teachers Perception of Universal Basic Education Scale” (COTPUBES) containing a total of 25 items which were administered on counsellors and the teachers. It consists of two parts: Sections A and B. Section A sought for bio-data of the respondents while section B is a 21-item scale. Each item has five rating scale of Excellent, Very Good, Average, Fair and Poor. The respondents were instructed to tick any of the options applicable to them.

The instrument was subjected to content and construct validity by three experts in Counselling, Measurement and Evaluation. In the course of validation, the experts subjected the items to criticism and vetting with respect to statement of problem, research questions, relevance and use of language; corrections were made as suggested by the experts. These efforts helped to ensure that the instrument had high content validity. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach alpha method of internal consistency. The instrument “Enhancing Quality in the Implementation of Universal Basic Education Scale” was pilot tested on 40 respondents who are not part of the participants for this study. The Cronbach alpha $r = 0.74$, $p < 0.05$ level of significance.

The researcher administered the questionnaire to the participants with the help of a counsellor or teacher in the school during the working hour for five days. The researcher was able to retrieve all the questionnaires administered. The data generated with the questionnaire were analysed with the use of t-test statistics, Chi-square and Analysis of Covariance (ANOVA).

Presentation of Result based on Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There will be no significant difference in the mean rating of counsellors and teachers about their roles in enhancing quality in the UBE programme implementation.

Table 1: t-test analysis on difference in the mean rating between counsellors and teachers about the roles in enhancing quality in the UBE programme implementation

Participants	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	P-value	P<0.05
Counsellors	100	2.6	2.22	98	0.18	0.87	Not Significant
Teachers	100	2.4	3.24				

The t-test analysis in Table 1 shows that the t-value of 0.18 is less than its corresponding P-value of 0.87, which implies that there is no statistical significant difference in the mean rating of counsellors and teachers about the roles in enhancing quality in the UBE programme implementation.

Hypothesis 2: There will be no significant difference in the perception of counsellors and teachers about the quality of UBE programme implementation.

Table 2: Chi square analysis of the perception of counsellors and teachers about quality of UBE programme implementation.

Participants	Responses		Total	Df	X ² cal	Critical value 0.05
	Agreed	Disagreed				
Counsellors	56 (28)	44 (22)	100	1	3.98	3.84
Teachers	57 (28.5)	43 (21.5)	100			
Total	113	87	200			

The critical Chi-square value at 0.05 level of significance = 3.84

The calculated Chi-square value = 3.98

Table 2 above shows that the calculated value of 3.98 is greater than the critical value of 3.84, therefore the null hypothesis is rejected which implies that both counsellors and teachers differ significantly in their perception about good quality of UBE programme implementation.

Hypothesis 3: There will be no significant difference in the opinion of counsellors and teachers about the extent to which UBE programme has reduced illiteracy through the provision of quality basic education.

Table 3: ANOVA summary of opinion of counsellors and teachers about the extent to which UBE programme has reduced illiteracy through the provision of quality basic education

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	22.358	2	10.179	2.712	2.683
Within Groups	870.477	196	4.141		
Total	892.834	198			

Table 3 shows that F_{cal} (2.712) is greater than Sig. (2.683) at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis was rejected ($F=2.712$, $P>0.05$). It implies that there was statistically significant difference in the opinion of practicing counsellors, counsellors in the classroom, and teachers about the extent to which UBE programme has reduced illiteracy through the provision of quality basic education

Discussion

The finding of the first hypothesis revealed that there was no statistically significant difference in the mean rating of counsellors and teachers about their roles in enhancing quality in the UBE programme implementation. This shows the importance of counsellors and teachers in the implementation of UBE programme. According to Eбенуwa-Okoh (2012), to achieve the goal of UBE guidance service is a vital tool that cannot be neglected in the implementation of the UBE program. This is because guidance provides services, programs and activities that assist counselee (learners) to identify their problems, enhance their potentials, develop social and coping skills in order to adjust themselves and become productive in the society. The finding is in agreement with Arhedo, Adomeh and Aluede (2009) who examined School Counsellors' Roles in the Implementation of Universal Basic Education (UBE) Scheme in Nigeria and concluded that Universal Basic Education is a programme that must be implemented with full guidance of the

school counsellors from the point of programme development to the point of its implementation; the school counsellor's services are indeed worthwhile and indispensable. It is in view of the relevance of these counsellors' roles that Aluede (2006) observed that the primary school child is in the process of transition from home to school and is faced with adjustment problem and therefore needs to be followed up with adequate guidance and counselling.

This study is also in agreement with the study of Taiwo (2015) as regards the important of teachers that no matter the extent of availability of physical and material resources, if teachers are not available, they remain unproductive until they are utilised by teachers. To him, no matter how promising the curriculum is, the ideas therein can only be brought to lime light through teachers. This is a pointer to the significance of teachers in the effective implementation of such laudable scheme as UBE in Nigeria.

The second hypothesis showed that both counsellors and teachers differ significantly in their perception about good quality of UBE programme implementation. If there is quality in the implementation of basic education, it will help to catapult the countries to rapid growth and the unavailability of it could pose a threat to stability of the nation's education system. This finding supports the previous researcher like Lucas, Alaka and Odozi (2014) in which the outcome of their study showed that although the policy document about UBE indicates government commitment to providing quality education, the country appears to be lagging behind in achieving the expected quality of education. Similarly, Onwubiko (2012) noted that the availability of facilities like library blocks, school assembly hall, office blocks, textbooks, tables, chairs, chalkboards, recreational facilities, charts, maps, computers, pencils, diaries, desks and so on will go a long way in ensuring the success of UBE scheme. This implies that more facilities, equipment and qualified teachers should be made available for the implementation of UBE programme in Lagos State for effectiveness of the scheme.

The third hypothesis revealed that there was statistically significant difference in the opinion of counsellors and teachers on the extent to which UBE programme has reduced illiteracy through the provision of quality universal basic education in Lagos State. This finding is in tandem with the position of Lucas, Alaka and Odozi (2014) that Nigeria has not been doing well in all her effort to achieve Millennium Development Goal (MDGS). The implementation guideline of the Universal Basic Education program (2013) proffers some strategies which include the fact that provision of educational program should be universal, free and compulsory and efforts are to be made to counter the factors that were impediments to the realization of previous education programs like the universal primary education are to aid effective implementation This has not been completely achieved.

This study also confirms Umo (2015) view that the Nigerian universal basic education programme must continue to work towards improving quantity and quality of universal basic education in order to increase access and provide the right education for Nigerian children. Primary school education must be focused on education to help children build confidence and desire to continue learn. Low learning achievement in primary school level could be traced to lack of preparedness for learning due to insubstantial investments in education.

Despite all the efforts of the Federal government to give the pupils quality education through universal basic education, a lot still needs to be done. The money allocated for education by government is less than internationally accepted of 15% of total budget so there is a lot of gap. The demand for education is growing higher everyday but the available resources are not keeping pace in terms of the development. Children who have not prepared well for learning in terms of sufficient material resources for schools, the number of teachers and their training, the amount of actual learning time, facilities and leadership have little chance of benefitting, their commitment to education is likely to diminish and they are more likely to drop out of school (EFA GMR 2012). Lucas, Alaka and Odozi (2014) also emphasised that to enhance proper teaching and learning process and for universal basic education to achieve its set goals there is a need to put certain educational materials, equipment and facilities in place. Library and laboratories should be well equipped and relevant teaching aids should be made available to teacher. The rationale behind this finding is that the scheme requires facilities and some other expectations from governments and other stake holders to be available in order to succeed and reduce literacy to the barest minimum. The absence of any of the basic requirement facilities can result to the failure of the programme implementation.

Conclusion

Universal Basic Education is a vital programme of nine (9) years, to build the declining and decaying education sector in Nigeria and to catch our children and youth, prepare and equip them for future materializing through appropriate quality education for them to play their quota in developing the nation. Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that teachers and counsellors are backbone of any educational programme. Since education is a major tool for the quick transformation of any nation, all hands must therefore be on deck by the stakeholders including counsellors to realise the set goals and objectives. Therefore, the usage of teacher and counsellors' skills at all levels to enhance quality of education cannot be over emphasized. It must also be said that to enhance proper teaching and learning process and for universal basic education to achieve its set goals, teaching and counselling service are essential service. It will help individual realise himself, help them to maximize benefits of living and to expose the students to affective domain to maximize the gains of cognitive and psychomotor domains for greater achievement in school. Creating values in education is germane if there must be quality in the implementation of UBE programme. A lot still needs to be done by government because the demand for education is growing higher everyday but the available resources are not keeping pace in terms of the development.

Implication and Recommendation

The implications of this study is that in achieving the goals and objectives of UBE programme, teaching, guidance and counselling are integral aspect of UBE programme, it entails that in-service training and skill acquisition programmes should always be organised for both teachers and counsellors to update their knowledge on daily basis to equip them with new ideas and modern technology that can make them to be more effective, more proactive and not

remedial as a stakeholder of UBE programme. School teachers and counsellors must team up with administrative staff in order to direct adequate and maximum utilisation of school resources by helping individual members of the school community to identify their benefits and personal responsibilities in handling the available resources to provide quality education.

Based on the finding of this study the following recommendations are proffered:

- Professional development, in-service-training, seminars and workshops should be organized periodically for school teachers and counsellors to keep abreast with current practices that can make UBE programme compete with education programmes in the world.
- Motivation and mentoring of teachers and counsellors will make them to perform more in providing support services for UBE to be more effective.
- One of the central functions of government at all levels is the provision of qualitative and sound education for the citizens therefore government should do more in educating her citizen through UBE by allocating more funds to education sector.
- More counsellors are needed as practising counsellors and not as counsellors in classroom for them to be more functional to teach values and skills through different counselling services. More teachers should be employed to allow the counsellors do the counselling work effectively.
- All the three tiers of government should provide facilities needed for guidance practice.
- Federal, state and local Governments need to encourage individuals and parents to be conscious of learning as a lifelong process so they should give their children universal basic education that they can be a successful member of the community and society at large.

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